

Metal ion induced dissolution of melanin extracted from the bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum*

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Manuscript received online 28 July 2013, accepted 11 September 2013

Abstract : Naturally occurring pigment, melanins, although participate in innumerable biological functions, has not been amenable for analyses due to its heterogeneous and insoluble nature. An effort has been made here to search for a few solvents that can dissolve melanin (extracted from bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum* as well as synthetic) to an appreciable amount to facilitate spectroscopic study towards its characterization. Moreover, as melanin has a high affinity for metal ions, interaction of melanins with metal ion(s) can be an avenue for enhancing the solubility of melanins in these solvents and can be utilized in various biotechnological applications.

Keywords : Bacterial melanin, synthetic melanin, metal ion, UV-Vis spectroscopy, FTIR spectroscopy.

Introduction

The ubiquitous naturally occurring pigment, melanins participate in innumerable biological functions, including protection against the ultraviolet radiation of sunlight¹. Research interest on melanins has been prompted by their occurrence in almost every biological system along with a varied range of functions in different organisms attributed to them. Along with the higher order of living organisms, melanins can also be found in microorganisms. Melanins protect these microorganisms (e.g. bacteria and fungi) against thermal as well as chemical (e.g. metals and oxidizing agents) and biochemical (e.g. host defenses against invading microbes) stresses² that involve cell damage by solar UV radiation through generation of reactive oxygen species. In spite of being responsible for a wide range of biological functions, this pigment has not been amenable to easy chemical and structural analyses because of its heterogeneous, insoluble nature and resistant to crystallization. The insoluble property of these brown/black naturally occurring pigments containing primarily the indole moiety (dihydroxyindole and dihydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid)³⁻⁵ precludes their study with solution-state hydrodynamic, spectroscopic and light-scattering techniques.

Melanin has a high affinity for metal ions and can act

both as a metal reservoir as well as a metal sink. By binding metal ion it sequesters metals, protecting them from reduction by cellular components and subsequent induction of oxidative stress⁶⁻⁸. Moreover, a number of hypotheses on the etiology of neurodegenerative diseases like Parkinson's and other CNS disorders postulate a role of metal ions and neuromelanin. It is found that pigmented cells contain higher amount of metal ion(s) as compared to non-melanized homologous tissues^{9,10}. Excess accumulation of several metals at certain conditions in neurons may trigger inflammatory and degenerative processes aggravating the underlying pathological condition¹¹. Thus abnormal environmental exposure to these metals is likely associated with increased incidence of Parkinson's Disease¹². Neuromelanin, having high affinity for these metals shown by the accumulation ratios; can protect against their neurotoxicity through interaction with metals by slowing disease progression¹¹. Hence, interaction with metal ion(s) is considered as one of the main biological functions of melanin. Studies have been carried out to understand the importance of interaction between metal ions and melanins towards determining the nature of the metal ion binding sites, binding affinity as well as to elucidate how metal binding plays in determining the physical, structural, biological, and photochemical properties of mela-

nins¹⁰⁻¹⁷. The carboxyl, the phenolic-OH or/and the NH of the indole moiety of melanins are considered as the potential sites for interaction with metal ions and the relative binding affinities are proposed in the order of $\text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Zn}^{2+} < \text{Fe}^{3+} < \text{Cu}^{2+}$ ¹⁰. However, the complete picture is yet to be obtained due to heterogeneous nature and insolubility of melanins in biological and almost all organic solvents.

At this juncture, it is important to search for a few solvents where melanins can be dissolved in an appreciable amount for pertaining spectroscopic study and to explore whether metal binding interaction can be used to enhance the solubility of melanins in those solvents. In this manuscript we are going to report interaction of melanins (obtained from bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum* as well as synthetic) with two alkaline earth metals (Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) in different pure and mixed solvents which reveals that metal ions can induce the solubility of melanins in solvents under study. This would bring an opportunity for studying the relevance of melanin in controlling/slowing disease progression through interaction with metal ion as metal-melanin interaction is hypothesized to play crucial role in several physiological disorders.

Experimental

Bacterial melanin has been obtained from the cells of bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum* by the method described by Whittaker¹⁸, while; synthetic melanin (used as control) has been purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (CAS No. 8049-97-6). In order to search for a few solvents that can dissolve melanins for spectroscopic study, a series of pure and mixed solvents (mixture of pure organic and water at different volume) have been tried and inference is drawn from the UV-Vis spectra obtained in the range of 800–200 nm using UV-2401 PC Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

To explore whether metal binding interaction can enhance the solubility of melanins in those particular solvents, interaction of melanins (obtained from bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum* as well as synthetic) with Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ion in these solvents are studied separately. From concentrated stock solution of individual metal ions [for Cu^{2+} , stock solution of CuSO_4 (conc. 10 mM) and for Zn^{2+} , solution of ZnSO_4 (conc. 10 mM)] a fixed amount of metal ion solution has been added at a regular

interval to the bacterial melanin and the synthetic melanin solutions separately, prepared in those different solvents, where an appreciable UV-Vis spectrum are obtained for melanins under study. The interaction studied are monitored using UV-Vis spectroscopy in the range of 800–200 nm in UV-2401 PC Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer instrument. Further, to nullify the contribution of simple metal-solvent interaction in the UV-Vis spectrum of the metal added melanin, equal concentration of the metal ion solution has been used in the reference cuvette (done in a double beam system).

Moreover, to confirm the interaction of metal ion with the bacterial melanin (obtained from bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum*) as well as synthetic melanin, FTIR spectrum of individual melanin and its Cu^{2+} -ion added species has been taken in KBr pellet. Cu^{2+} -ion added species of bacterial melanin (as well as synthetic melanin) has been prepared by adding the bacterial melanin to the high concentration of CuSO_4 and kept for 15 days. The mixture is centrifuged, washed thoroughly with 0.01 mol l^{-1} HCl (to eliminate weakly adsorbed Cu^{2+} ions); then several times with deionized water and lyophilized¹⁹. The solid material thus obtained then is used for taking FTIR spectrum. FT-IR absorption spectrum has been obtained at 25 °C, using 4 cm^{-1} resolution with 8 number of scans in Bx Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer Spectrum 1000.

Results and discussion

Solubility of bacterial and synthetic melanins :

It is well known that melanins are well soluble in NaOH/KOH solution, giving a very broad UV-Vis spectrum in the range of 550–200 nm. As NaOH and KOH are strong solvent and not recommended for several studies due to their pH in strong basic region, it is necessary to find out some other solvents, which can dissolve melanins to an appreciable quantity for pursuing different spectroscopic studies. It has been reported that ethyleneglycolmonoethyl ether, or a mixture of ethyl lactate and benzyl alcohol (6 : 4 by vol : vol) can dissolve melanin extracted from ink sac of *Sepia officinalis* and melanoma tissues²⁰. In order to find out alternative solvent(s) for dissolving melanin extracted from the bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum* (bacterial melanin), similar effort has been initiated here, for which a series of pure organic

solvents are taken and to that different volumes of water are mixed (mixed solvents) and solubility of bacterial as well as synthetic melanins in those solvents has been studied (adding melanin sample as 0.05 mg in 1 ml of solvent) by measuring absorbance using UV-Vis spectroscopic technique. The results show that pure 1,4-dioxane, and a few mixed solvents e.g. ethyleneglycolmonomethyl ether with 10% H₂O (EME with 10% H₂O), ethyleneglycolmonoethyl ether with 10% H₂O (EEE with 10% H₂O), ethylenediamine with 15% H₂O (EDA with 10% H₂O) can dissolve melanin in an appreciable amount to produce considerable UV-Vis spectrum for bacterial melanin (Fig. 1a) as well as synthetic melanin (data not shown). However, the comparative UV-Vis study suggests that bacterial melanin can be better dissolved in ethylenediamine (15% H₂O), while synthetic melanin is better dissolved in ethylenediamine (15% H₂O) and ethyleneglycolmonoethyl ether (10% H₂O).

Interaction with metal ions :

UV-Vis studies :

On gradual addition of Cu²⁺ ion (in the range of concentration 0–500 μM; where concentration of highest Cu²⁺ ion approximately 6 times higher than that of melanin concentration) to the bacterial melanin in 1,4-dioxane, intensity of the absorbance of the initial peaks at 242 and 292 nm obtained without Cu²⁺ ion, increases gradually (Fig. 1b) and attains saturation at higher concentration of metal ion (Figs. 1b, 2a). However, upon addition of Cu²⁺ ion the rate of enhancement of the OD value of 242 nm peak (having maximum bathochromic shift of 3 nm at the highest concentration of Cu²⁺ ion) occurs at much higher rate in comparison to that of 292 nm peak (Figs. 1b, 2a).

A similar observation is obtained for the synthetic melanin upon successive addition of Cu²⁺ ion (Fig. 2a). However, the increment of OD at 242 nm peak is comparatively lower than that observed for the bacterial melanin although its rate of increment is higher in comparison to the rate of increment of 292 nm peak in the same species (Fig. 2a).

On the contrary, in the mixed solvents (e.g. ethyleneglycolmonomethyl ether with 10% H₂O, ethyleneglycolmonoethyl ether with 10% H₂O, ethylenediamine with 15% H₂O) instead of double maxima found in 1,4-dioxane, only one appreciable single maximum (in

the range of 260–300 nm) with a shoulder/hump (≥350 nm) is observed for the bacterial as well as the synthetic melanins. In all the solvent systems for both the melanins intensity of the absorbance value at the λ_{max} increases upon gradual addition of Cu²⁺ ion (having maximum bathochromic shift of ~3 nm) and reaches a saturation value at higher concentration of Cu²⁺ ion as observed in 1,4-dioxane (Figs. 2b, c).

A similar result of increasing the intensity of the absorbance value of the λ_{max} is also obtained in all the solvents for the bacterial melanin upon addition of Zn²⁺ ion (Figs. 3a, b) and confirms the interaction of melanin with both the metal ions. However, upon addition of Cu²⁺ ion to melanin the increase of intensity of absorbance is higher than that observed upon addition of Zn²⁺ ion; suggesting better interaction between Cu²⁺ and melanin. This is in accordance to the proposed relative binding affinities of the metal ions to melanin : Zn²⁺ < Cu²⁺ ¹⁰; although the binding constant values cannot be reported as the concentration of melanins cannot be measured properly (the molecular weight and the molar extinction coefficient of melanin are still unknown due to its heterogeneous, insoluble/colloidal nature). The overall observation of UV-Vis spectra especially the appearance of double maxima in 1,4-dioxane is very similar to that found for interaction of Cu²⁺ ion with the synthetic dihydroxyindole (DHI) melanin, considered to be one of the basic constituents of natural melanin¹⁵.

On an ardent scrutiny, it can be highlighted that the overall changes in UV-Vis spectra of melanins upon addition of metal ion(s) in all the solvents, follow a sigmoidal path, pointing towards single turn over reaction. Further, no significant shift in λ_{max} values for both the bacterial and synthetic melanins upon addition of the Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ metal ions, can rule out the possibility of formation of charge transfer complex between melanin and metal ion. This observation certainly emphasizes that the metal ion(s) upon interaction with melanins does not rupture the basic chromophore of the melanin system, rather participates in shifting the equilibrium between the insoluble and soluble part of melanins (considered to be colloidal pigments¹⁵) towards the soluble component which enhances the absorbance value of melanin at all solvents under study (Fig. 1c). Thus, at the highest concentration of metal ion(s) (especially in presence of Cu²⁺) the amount

Fig. 1. (a) Overlay of UV-Vis spectra (800–210 nm) of bacterial melanin in different solvents under study (see text) which demonstrate that these solvent can dissolve bacterial melanin in an appreciable amount to produce considerable UV-Vis spectrum. (b) Overlay of UV-Vis spectra (800–210 nm) of bacterial melanin in 1,4-dioxane showing gradual enhancement of absorbance without shifting of λ_{max} upon gradual addition of Cu^{2+} ion. (c) Overlay of UV-Vis spectra (800–210 nm) of bacterial melanin in different solvents under study (see text) at highest concentration of Cu^{2+} ion showing a few fold enhancement of absorbance value of melanin in comparison to metal free system in each solvent.

of dissolved melanin is a few fold excess than that in metal-free system. Similar to that of the metal DHI-melanin interaction¹⁵, interaction of metal ion with melanins under study establishes the complexation with the metal ion through chelation that would promote deprotonation of the acidic melanin sites (catechol groups) which is supported by the increase of the absorbance at ~250 nm with each addition of metal ion at a higher rate than the absorbance at ≥ 300 nm (Fig. 1b). Further, appearance of the double maxima, especially in dioxane, may indicate interaction of metal ion(s) with the tautomeric forms of the melanin constituents (dihydroxyindole \rightleftharpoons quinoneimine) where the interaction with the dihydroxy group is overriding upon addition of metal ion. However, in the mixed solvents this dynamic equilibrium may

shift more towards the dihydroxy form from the initial phase (due to presence of water) and results towards single maximum.

Infra-red studies :

Interaction of metal ion with melanins through complex formation is further justified from the FTIR spectrum of Cu^{2+} -ion bound bacterial as well as synthetic melanin. The enhancement of the overall absorbance of melanin spectrum upon addition of metal ion in comparison to the metal free system, as observed in UV-Vis studies, stands in its support. Comparison of the FTIR spectrum (in absorbance mode) for Cu^{2+} -ion bound bacterial melanin with its metal free form shows characteristic lowering of OH stretching frequency from $\sim 3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to

Fig. 2. (a) Enhancement of absorbance value at λ_{max} 242 and 292 nm of bacterial melanin and synthetic melanin in 1,4-dioxane pointing towards a single turn over reaction upon gradual addition of Cu^{2+} ion. (b) Enhancement of absorbance value at a particular λ_{max} of bacterial melanin in different mixed solvents under study (see text) pointing towards a single turn over reaction upon gradual addition of Cu^{2+} ion. (c) Enhancement of absorbance value at a particular λ_{max} of synthetic melanin in different mixed solvents under study (see text) pointing towards a single turn over reaction upon gradual addition of Cu^{2+} ion.

Fig. 3. (a) Enhancement of absorbance value at a particular λ_{max} of bacterial and synthetic melanin in 1,4-dioxane pointing towards a single turn over reaction upon gradual addition of Zn^{2+} ion. (b) Enhancement of absorbance value at a particular λ_{max} of bacterial melanin in different mixed solvents pointing towards a single turn over reaction upon gradual addition of Zn^{2+} ion.

Fig. 4. Comparison of FTIR spectrum of bacterial melanin with and without addition of Cu^{2+} ion in absorbance mode highlighting the participation of OH- group of melanin for metal interaction.

$\sim 3250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 4) upon addition of metal ion. This clearly indicates that phenolic-OH group of melanin comprises the basic binding site for metal ion complexation. This is similar to binding of Cu^{2+} to *Sepia* eumelanin, where it has been concluded that the hydroxyl functional group is responsible for Cu^{2+} binding²¹. Similar result is obtained for synthetic melanin also (data not shown).

Model for metal ion interaction :

Both the UV-Vis and FTIR studies demonstrate the interaction of alkaline earth metal ion(s) (Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) with bacterial as well as synthetic melanins in various solvents, enhancing the solubility of both the melanins in respective solvents. Moreover, interaction of metal ion(s) preserving the basic chromophore of the melanin system with a single turn over reaction, may suggest that one of the OH groups of o-OH (catechol) may be deprotonated to bind to Cu^{2+} in this bacterial (as well as synthetic) melanin, as observed for Cu^{2+} bound to *Sepia* eumelanin through biophysical and biochemical studies^{21,22}. The second OH group of o-OH (catechol) system may interact with the metal ion through coordinate bond to satisfy the coordination of the metal ion and thus weakening the O-H bond strength which is validated by lowering of O-H frequency in IR studies.

Conclusion

In lieu of NaOH, 1,4-dioxane and mixed solvents (e.g. ethyleneglycolmonomethyl ether with 10% H_2O ,

ethyleneglycolmonoethyl ether with 10% H_2O , ethylenediamine with 15% H_2O) can act as alternative solvents for dissolving naturally occurring pigment, melanin extracted from the bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum* to an appreciable amount for facilitating spectroscopic study. As bacterial melanin has a high affinity for metal ion, interaction of this melanin with metal ion(s) will be an avenue for enhancing the solubility of bacterial melanin in these solvents. Moreover, a detailed knowledge of such metal-melanin interaction would promote to further study the defense mechanisms through leaching out the accumulated metals towards controlling diseases like Parkinson's and a few others where accumulation of several metal ions play a crucial role in the pathogenesis.

Acknowledgement

Authors are indebted to Department of Biophysics, Bose Institute for recording the UV-Vis spectra and IICB and IACS for recording the FTIR spectra.

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